

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE OF COMMINGLED UNIFABRIC CF/PEEK COMPOSITES WITH DIFFERENT CONSOLIDATION QUALITY

Andrew Beehag and Lin Ye*
Centre for Advanced Materials Technology
Department of Mechanical and Mechatronic Engineering
The University of Sydney, NSW 2006, AUSTRALIA

ABSTRACT

The influence of consolidation quality on interlaminar fracture of commingled CF/PEEK composite was studied. Holding time was varied to alter consolidation levels in the processed composite. Consolidation quality was studied through void content and density measurement, while transverse flexural (TF) properties were correlated with processing conditions. Mode-I and -II interlaminar fracture was studied using double cantilever beam (DCB) and end notch flexure (ENF) specimens. The results indicated that consolidation quality was improved with increased holding time. Mode-I interlaminar fracture behaviour had little correlation with consolidation quality, while apparent mode-II interlaminar fracture toughness decreased with reduced void content. Consolidation quality is not the only aspect which controls interlaminar fracture properties.

INTRODUCTION

High performance thermoplastic composite materials have attracted much research attention in recent years, due to the advantages they present of generally high toughness, good hot and wet performance and solvent resistance [1]. However, the high viscosity of the matrix during processing has limited their commercial use. One solution is to use a prepregged tape (e.g. APC-2) as a composite preform. An alternative is to use a novel preform, such as the commingled yarn [2]. In this system, matrix fibres are spun and dispersed in the reinforcing fibre tows, giving the matrix proximity to the final position in the consolidated composite. A major consideration for the processing of thermoplastic composites is the consolidation quality. It is important to have a comprehensive understanding of in-situ consolidation mechanisms of the final product. Where incomplete consolidation occurs, it is also important to determine the effect of this on mechanical performance of the product, detrimental or otherwise.

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effects of processing conditions, in particular the holding time, on the consolidation quality, and the resulting interlaminar fracture performance of unidirectional commingled CF/PEEK composites. Consolidation quality is characterised measuring void content and density of the consolidated composite panels, as well as transverse

* corresponding author

flexural (TF) properties. Interlaminar fracture properties are determined using double cantilever beam (DCB) and end notch flexure (ENF) tests.

MATERIAL AND PROCESSING PROCEDURE

The material used in this study was commingled carbon fibre/PEEK unidirectional prepreg (UD AS4 3K/PEEK) supplied by the Polymer Research Division, BASF. Unidirectional prepreg mats were produced through "edge-welding" the unidirectional prepreg with a soldering iron into 200×200 mm squares with subsequent cutting, which were then placed into a steel mould and consolidated with a laboratory hot press. The 20 layers of prepreg gave a subsequent panel thickness of approximately 3 mm after consolidation. A 25 µm Upilex® film insert, coated with release agent, was used to produce a starter crack of 60 mm in length in the midplane of the panels, which was used for the following mode-I and -II interlaminar fracture tests. The processing cycles of the composite are outlined in Fig. 1. All panels were manufactured at an applied pressure of 1 MPa and processing temperature of 400°C, with the holding time set at 10, 30 or 60 minutes. Each panel was then cooled with the hot press, at an applied pressure slightly higher than atmospheric pressure, giving an average cooling rate of 3 °C/min.

Figure 1. Typical processing cycle of commingled CF/PEEK composites

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Sketches of the transverse flexure (TF), mode-I double cantilever beam (DCB) and mode-II end notched flexure (ENF) specimens used for characterisation are shown in Fig. 2. Mode-I tests were conducted on an Instron 4302 machine at a cross-head rate of 1 mm/min. Evaluation of crack growth resistance, G_{IC} , was conducted using the method based on corrected beam theory [3]. Fracture was characterised by both stable and unstable crack propagation, therefore three values of G_{IC} were evaluated, i.e. $G_{IC, prop}$ is defined at the maximum load point obtained just before unstable crack growth; $G_{IC, reinit}$ is the value at the initiation point of stable crack propagation; $G_{IC, arr}$ is the arrest value, where unstable crack growth ceases. The initiation point of stable crack propagation is assumed to occur at the starting point of non-linearity in each section of the load-displacement curve. Mode-II ENF interlaminar fracture specimens were tested at a cross-head loading rate of 0.5 mm/min. G_{IIc} was evaluated using the method based on experimental compliance calibration [3]. Transverse flexure (TF) tests were conducted at a cross-head rate of 1.2 mm/min, according to the ASTM E790M standard [4].

The void content of the commingled CF/PEEK composites was determined with two separate methods. Image analysis was applied to measure void content polished cross sections, determined as a percentage of surface area. In all cases, an average of 6 measurements of void content was taken from a similar location in each panel. Furthermore, theoretical density could be calculated from constituent properties:

$$\rho_t = \frac{\rho_f \rho_m}{W_f \rho_m + W_m \rho_f} \quad (1)$$

where ρ_f and ρ_m are the density of fibre and matrix respectively, and W_f and W_m the volume fractions of fibre and matrix respectively. Then the apparent void content of a composite can be determined from

$$X_v = \frac{\rho_t - \rho_e}{\rho_t} \quad (2)$$

where ρ_e is the density measured experimentally. In this case the density was evaluated for each testing specimen individually, and then an average density calculated for each processing cycle. There was negligible squeeze-out of the matrix during processing, so density measurement was a reliable indicator of consolidation quality. Cross-sectional void measurement using image analysis was prone to wide variation, but provided extra information on the size and distribution of voids resulting from manufacturing.

Figure 2. Schematics of specimens for mechanical characterisation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Consolidation Quality

Figure 3 shows cross-sections of the CF/PEEK composites manufactured with holding times of 10, 30 and 60 minutes respectively, which indicate the time dependent impregnation steps. The quantity and size of voids in the composites are clearly reduced for a long holding time (Fig. 3c), i.e. consolidation quality is improved. A comparison between the image analysis results and those obtained through direct density measurements shows that the image analysis gives a similar trend in void content variation (Figure 4). The large voids observed in the micrographs (see Fig. 3a) may be attributed to the particular structure of the commingled preform. As illustrated in Fig. 1, a pressure of 1 MPa was applied only during the constant temperature stage of the processing

cycle, which ensured that consolidation occurred in the desired time periods, i.e. 10, 30 or 60 minutes. This procedure, however, does not account for low pressure (100 - 200 kPa) applied at the cooling stage, which may result in increased void content in the consolidated composites.

Figure 3. Micrographs for time dependent consolidation of commingled CF/PEEK composite for (a) 10 mins; (b) 30 mins; (c) 60 mins.

Figure 4. Void content versus holding time for commingled CF/PEEK composites.

Furthermore, the fibre bundles in one layer of the CF/PEEK commingled prepreg do not conform very well to those in adjacent layers during processing. The prepreg layer is not perfectly flat, and the commingled fibre bundles were not under tension when laid up, which results in angle misalignment between fibre bundles in adjacent layers, and between the fibres within a bundle. Therefore the molten PEEK matrix is required to fill spaces between fibre bundles, as well as inside them. It has been found that an unmingling process may occur during processing of thermoplastic composites with commingled yarn preforms [5,6], where the matrix fibres initially melt and leave the reinforcing fibre bundles, forming matrix pools surrounding the dry fibres. As pressure is applied, the matrix pools coalesce, and finally matrix impregnates back into the dry fibre tows. This mechanism can be seen in Fig. 3 where large voids outside the fibre bundles are only apparent for the short holding time (Fig. 3a), and voids inside the fibre bundles are gradually reduced when the holding time is increased (Fig. 3b, 3c).

Figures 5 and 6 display the transverse flexural properties of the CF/PEEK composites against the void content. Although significant scatter exists in the experimental data, an apparent trend between the transverse flexural properties and void content/density can be observed. One can state that transverse flexure properties of the commingled CF/PEEK composites are improved.

Figure 5. Transverse flexural modulus versus void content for commingled CF/PEEK composites

Figure 6. Transverse flexural strength versus void content for commingled CF/PEEK composites.

Mode-I Fracture

Stable and unstable crack growth was found in the commingled CF/PEEK composites. Normally small periods of stable crack growth (0.5 - 2 mm) were followed by unstable crack growth (5 - 15 mm). Poorly consolidated commingled CF/PEEK composites had crack growth characterised by a series of short unstable crack jumps of approximately 5 mm, compared to 10 - 15 mm in the well consolidated composites. In the commingled yarn based composite, slight angle mismatch in the reinforcing fibre bundles between adjacent prepreg layers can also limit the amount of fibre bridging formed behind the crack tip [7]. Fibre bridging, which is present in some test specimens, was never at a consistent level, consequently giving a wide variation in the fracture energy.

Conversely, consolidation of commingled yarn without tension in the fibre direction may result in a "wavy lamina" in the consolidated composites, giving a highly irregular interlaminar crack path (i.e. not flat), with a resultant high apparent fracture toughness [8]. It can be seen that little correlation exists between the consolidation quality and mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness (Fig. 7). As with the previous discussion, variables other than consolidation quality may have a significant influence on the magnitude of the G_{IC} value. In particular, a significant amount of fibre bridging was observed in the composites manufactured for a holding time of 10 minutes. Conversely, Fig. 8a shows the fracture surface of the composite where interfacial failure occurred. This indicates that the bonding between the carbon fibre and the PEEK matrix is poor for a holding time of 10 minutes, compared to the good bonding (Fig. 8b) for a long holding time (60 min). The influence of consolidation on G_{IC} can therefore not be easily isolated from other variables. Nevertheless an increase in the holding time was found to give better adhesion of the PEEK to the carbon fibres.

Figure 7. Mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness versus void content for commingled CF/PEEK composites.

Figure 8. SEM micrographs showing mode-I crack growth in commingled CF/PEEK composites for (a) 10 mins; (b) 60 mins.

Mode-II Fracture

The commingled CF/PEEK composites normally failed in an unstable manner in mode-II ENF tests. In contrast to the mode-I cases, it can be seen that mode-II interlaminar fracture toughness of the commingled CF/PEEK composite is clearly increased at a high void content, as displayed in Fig. 9. Polished sections of the mode-II specimens, displayed in Fig. 10, show that multiple cracking (side cracking) occurred beside the main fracture plane for the composites processed for a short holding time, which would raise the apparent fracture energy measured. By contrast, well consolidated commingled CF/PEEK composites displayed no apparent multi-crack growth beside the main fracture plane (Fig. 10b).

Figure 9. Mode-II apparent interlaminar fracture toughness versus holding time for commingled CF/PEEK composites.

Figure 10. Polished cross sections showing crack growth mechanisms in mode-II fracture of commingled CF/PEEK composites consolidated for (a) 10 mins; (b) 60 mins.

CONCLUSION

The consolidation quality of commingled unifabric CF/PEEK composites and its effect on interlaminar fracture behaviour was investigated. Increasing the holding time from 10 to 60 minutes clearly improved the consolidation quality of the composites, as illustrated by the reduction of void content and/or the increase in the density of the consolidated composites. The void percentage measured on polished cross-sections using image analysis gave similar results to the density measurement, although one can argue that density measurement may be a more reliable indicator of consolidation quality. Mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness had little direct

correlation with the consolidation quality. Other factors, such as fibre bridging behind the crack tip, may have a significant influence on G_{IC} values. However, mode-II apparent fracture toughness, G_{IIC} , was found to have an clear increase with a reduced consolidation quality, i.e. with high void content.

The microstructure of the composite preforms, such as the arrangement of commingled yarn bundles into unifabrics, has significant effects on the bundle alignment in the consequent consolidated composites. Discrete angles between the fibre bundles promoted the formation of voids in the finished composites. Consolidating the composite under slight tension, to straighten the reinforcing fibres, may eliminate this problem, but would add complexity to the manufacturing process.

In conclusion, characterisations of the relationship between consolidation quality and the corresponding mechanical property profile is an essential aspect in manufacturing of thermoplastic composite materials from the cost-effective preforms. Manufacture, repair and replacement of thermoplastic composite components in the future will rely on a readily quantifiable data base of performance. Further work in this area is required to provide comprehensive knowledge for composite applications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Thanks are due to the Polymer Research Division, BASF, Germany, for supplying the testing materials. L. Ye thanks the Australian Research Council (ARC) for supporting this study with a large research grant (AB-9332172). A. Beehag is supported by a postgraduate scholarship from the Department of Mechanical and Mechatronic Engineering, the University of Sydney, and an ARC postgraduate supplementary scholarship.

REFERENCES

- [1] Chang I.Y., Lees J.K., Recent Development in Thermoplastic Composites: A Review of Matrix Systems and Processing Methods, *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 1 (1988) 277-95.
- [2] Olson S.H., Manufacturing with commingled yarns, fabrics and powder prepreg thermoplastic composite materials, *SAMPE Journal* 26 (5) (1990) 31-36.
- [3] European Group on Fracture, Polymer & Composites Task Group, A protocol for interlaminar fracture testing of composites, 1988.
- [4] ASTM E790M - Standard test methods for flexural properties of unreinforced and reinforced plastics and electrical insulating materials.
- [5] Ye L., Friedrich K., Kastle J., Mai Y.-W., Manufacturing of CF/PEEK composites from commingled yarn preforms, *Composites Science and Technology* (submitted in July 1994).
- [6] Van West B.P., Pipes R.B., Advani S.G., The consolidation of thermoplastic fabrics, *Polymer Composites*, 12 (1991) 417-427.
- [7] Johnson W.S., Mangalgiri P.D., Investigation of fiber bridging in double cantilever beam specimens, *Journal of Composites Technology and Research*, 9 (1) (1987) 10-13.
- [8] Ye L., Friedrich K., Mode I interlaminar fracture of co-mingled yarn based glass/polypropylene composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, 46 (1993) 187-198.